

Effect of Chemicals on Protein Hydrolysate Amino Acids of Pumpkin (*Cucurbita pepo*) Seeds During Germination

(Miss) C. C. KOTCHA, (Mrs.) J. A. OZA and D. N. VYAS

University Department of Chemistry, Bhavnagar University, Bhavnagar-364 002

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Seventeen amino acids of the acid protein hydrolysate of the germinating pumpkin (*Cucurbita pepo*) seeds treated with different chemicals were determined by circular paper chromatography. Qualitative distribution of acid hydrolysate amino acids varied a little in various treatments but appreciable quantitative change was observed during the studied span of germination. For most of the amino acids, the decrease in the protein hydrolysate amino acids during germination was associated with an increase in free amino acids. Potassium chloride has pronounced influence on nutritive value with respect to contents of essential amino acids than the mixed treatment. The results are discussed with respect to effect of soaking method, effects of chemicals on mitochondrial function and on the metabolites of the seedlings, and on the basis of mutual effects of the metabolites produced, on the contents of protein hydrolysate amino acids.

NUTRITIVE importance of proteins and dependence of animals on plants for these substances were first pointed out by Mulder¹. Good deal of work²⁻⁶ on the nutritive value of plant proteins has been done and it is reported that only intact proteins could be satisfactorily utilized for nutrition. It was further concluded that protein nutrition is essentially amino acid nutrition⁷⁻¹⁰. The essential and dietary proteins supply the building blocks for formation of tissue proteins, enzymes etc. Cereals, pulses, nuts and oilseeds form important part of Indian diet.

Studies on the effect of chemicals on germination of seeds date as far back as 1956. Swaminathan and Natrajan¹¹ reported that germination of several seeds was retarded when they were soaked in different oils. Very little work is reported on the effect of chemicals viz. fertilizers, growth regulators, on the chemical composition, especially on protein hydrolysate amino acids, of seeds during germination. As a part of our study on the effect of fertilizers and growth regulators on morphological changes and chemical constituents of cucurbitaceae seeds we have studied the effect of some chemicals, viz. fertilizers and growth regulators, on the protein hydrolysate amino acids of pumpkin seeds and the results are reported here.

Experimental

The process of pre-soaking treatment of the seeds and the mode of germination were the same as described in our previous work^{12,13}. The following conditions were adopted for the soaking treatments.

Soaking period : 2 hr ; pH of the medium : 7.0.

Chemicals and their concentrations :

A.	Fertilizers	(mg/100 ml)
(i)	Potassium chloride (PC)	90
(ii)	Urea (Ur)	150
(iii)	Sodium phosphate (SP)	100
B.	Growth Regulators	(mg/100 ml)
(i)	Gibberellic acid (GA)	30
(ii)	Ascorbic acid (AA)	90
(iii)	Maleic hydrazide (MH)	50
(iv)	Sulphanilamide (SA)	50
C.	Mixed treatment	(mg/100 ml)
(i)	PC+AA (MT)	90+90
D.	Distilled water (DW)	—

Method of extraction : The material left out from 100 mg cake of the treated and the untreated (control) seeds or seedlings after extraction of free amino acids and of lower (small) peptides was taken in a round bottom flask to which hydrochloric acid (approx. 10 ml ; 6.0M.) was added. Hydrolysis was carried out for 24 hr at 110°-115°. On completion of the hydrolysis the contents were cooled and the solution filtered. The filtrate containing interfering material was desalted by keeping it on regenerated I.R. 120 resin for 24 hr and then allowing it to pass through. The absorbed amino acids on the resin were eluted with 3.0 M ammonia solution. The elution was repeated 8 to 10 times. Ninhydrin test was done to make sure of the completion of elution. The eluent was evaporated on water bath and the thin film so obtained was dissolved in iso-propanol (10% v/v) and adjusted to a final volume of 2.0 ml for chromatographic analysis.

Chromatographic separation and estimation : The protein hydrolysate amino acids of the treated and

the control seeds at the studied periods of germination were determined by circular paper chromatography following essentially the procedure described by Krishnamurthy and Swaminathan¹⁴. The results were evaluated statistically and the relative errors in case of the various amino acids of different growth periods were in the range of 10 to 15%.

Results and Discussion

In the present study, in all 17 amino acids were detected in the acid protein hydrolysate. Qualitative distribution of acid hydrolysate amino acids varied a little in different treatments but the quantitative change was appreciable during the studied growth periods.

Fifteen amino acids viz., Cystine (433 µg/g), Arginine (2644 µg/g), Alanine (582 µg/g), Aspartic acid (1374 µg/g), Glutamic acid (3341 µg/g), Glutamine (3340 µg/g), Glycine (2795 µg/g), Histidine (2800 µg/g), Leucine (2538 µg/g), Tyrosine (3797 µg/g), Lysine (1163 µg/g), Methionine (488 µg/g), Phenylalanine (750 µg/g), Valine (375 µg/g) and Threonine (1269 µg/g) were found maximum in seeds treated with PC, MT, DW and the control ones. They were found to decrease with the period of germination except for Cystine and Arginine which were found to decrease up to the 8th and the 10th day of germination respectively and to increase thereafter. Asparagine (2956 µg/g) and Serine (1225 µg/g) were found maximum in the Ur treatment. Asparagine content decreased up to the 10th day while that of Serine throughout the period of germination.

In the growth regulator treatments Cystine (637 µg/g), Arginine (1353 µg/g), Asparagine (2784 µg/g), Glycine (824 µg/g), Histidine (1202 µg/g), Lysine (818 µg/g), Methionine (521 µg/g) and Phenylalanine (679 µg/g) were found maximum in the AA treated seeds and their contents, except that of Arginine, decreased with the progress of germination. The amount of Arginine decreased up to the 8th day of germination but thereafter recorded an increase. Histidine content was found decreasing upto the 6th day. Thereafter, it increased up to the 8th day and again decreased up to the 12th day. In MH treated seeds, Alanine (802 µg/g), Leucine (2143 µg/g), Tyrosine (2350 µg/g) and Valine (334 µg/g) were found maximum and their contents decreased gradually over the period of germination. However, in case of Leucine a slow and steady decrease in its content was marked up to the 4th day of germination. Aspartic acid (2330 µg/g) and Glutamic acid (351 µg/g) were found maximum in GA treated seeds and their amounts were found decreasing throughout the period of germination.

From the amounts of acid hydrolysate amino acids at the reported maxima of the various free amino acids in different cases¹⁷ it is noted that, except Asparagine in GA treatment, acid hydrolysate

amino acids decreased with the periods of germination in all the cases. Asparagine content of acid hydrolysate amino acids of GA treated seeds was found increasing from the 10th day of germination. Comparing the present results with our studies on free amino acids in the seedlings during germination, it is noted that for most of the amino acids, a decrease in acid hydrolysate amino acids took place simultaneously with an increase in free amino acid. Similar observations were recorded by Hegazi¹⁵ in case of germinating broad beans. The results suggest liberation of free amino acid as a result of hydrolysis of bound amino acid with progress of germination. The varied effects of chemicals on the amino acid contents are likely to be the effects of the chemicals on mitochondria during the soaking treatment.

Total amino acid (i.e. FFA*+LPAA*+PHAA*) was calculated for each treatment for all the periods of germination and the following conclusions were drawn.

Total amounts of Asparagine, in PC treatment, Threonine in DW treatment and Histidine in Ur and SA treatments increased throughout the periods of germination. Further, the total amount of amino acid was comparatively low than the amounts in other treatments in initial stages and in some cases even up to the end of the studied periods. The results suggest that the reported amino acids in the respective treatments must have synthesised during germination but the rate of their utilization was higher at the initial periods than at the later periods. Further, the total amounts of certain amino acids increased regularly up to certain periods of germination and then decreased as shown below :

PC-Alanine (8th day) ; GA-Leucine (8th day) ; MH-Histidine (4th day) ; MT-Alanine, Lysine, Threonine (5th day) and Histidine, Serine (7th day) DW-Leucine (5th day) and Lysine, Glutamine, Histidine and Serine (8th day) ; Control-Alanine (7th day).

These results suggest that the relative rate of synthesis of the amino acids was higher than their utilization at the initial stages of germination. Subramanian¹⁸ also reported a relative increase in protein synthesis during early germination of mung bean and runner bean. Dontsova¹⁷, while studying nitrogen compounds in the initial stages of growth of cotton seeds reported that the increase of amino acids in cotyledons was caused by proteolysis and the resulting free amino acids were used for protein synthesis. The increase of total amino acids in the present study may be because of such a route.

In order to know the relative effect of chemicals, total amounts of amino acids of treated seeds were

* FFA=Free amino acid ; LPAA=Lower peptide amino acid , PHAA=Protein hydrolysate amino acid.

compared with the amounts of DW treated seeds for each period of germination. In the following cases, total amounts of amino acids increased in comparison to DW treated seeds throughout the periods of germination.

PC - Alanine, Arginine, Aspartic acid, Cystine, Glutamine, Glutamic acid, Glycine, Histidine, Leucine, Lysine, Methionine, Phenylalanine, Serine, Threonine, Tyrosine and Valine.

Ur - Arginine, Glycine, Serine.

SP - Arginine.

GA - Arginine, Asparagine, Glycine, Leucine and Serine.

AA - Arginine, Glycine and Valine.

MH - Arginine, Glutamine, Leucine and Serine.

MT - Arginine, Glutamine, Glycine, Leucine, Lysine and Valine.

Control - Arginine and Serine.

From the above it is concluded that either the relative rates of synthesis of the reported amino acids in specific treatments are higher than that of the DW treated seeds or their utilization in the development of the seedlings must be lower.

The trend is as under :

PC > MT > GA > MH > Ur $\approx$ MH > AA > Control > SP.

The trend, as shown above, suggests that PC has pronounced influence on nutritive value with respect to contents of essential amino acids than MT treatment. In case of control seeds two amino acids had a higher total than DW treated seeds which might be due to adverse effect of soaking treatment.

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